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Sharing digital
arts and humanities
knowledge

Annual Report 2013

Table of Contents

- 1. Welcome to the DARIAH-EU Annual Report 2013 3
- 2. Key Objectives for 2013..... 4
- 3. Key achievements in 2013 4
 - 3.1. Take significant steps towards establishing the DARIAH ERIC..... 4
 - 3.2. Increase visibility of DARIAH activities throughout Europe..... 5
 - 3.3. Integrate and coordinate national DARIAH activities at the European level 7
 - 3.4. Organise the scientific and technical integration of DARIAH activities 8
 - 3.5. Implement an interim governance structure for the DARIAH ERIC.....10
 - 3.6. Identify opportunities for DARIAH in Horizon 2020 11
- 4. DARIAH activities 2013: a visual journey 11

1. Welcome to the DARIAH-EU Annual Report 2013

It is our great pleasure to welcome you to our Annual Report for 2013 and to introduce you to some of the highlights of our activities explored further in the following pages.

This year we have taken further significant steps towards establishing our European legal entity, the DARIAH ERIC, which will be an essential foundation for developing DARIAH as a sustainable infrastructure for digital arts and humanities research. Although the final phase of the process will be completed in 2014, we are delighted to already have the formal commitment of nine Founding Members; Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, The Netherlands and Slovenia.

In September we were delighted to launch our new [DARIAH-EU website](#). It is intended to be a first entry point for the European digital arts and humanities research community to find high-quality information about resources and services from our DARIAH partner institutions. Please take a look! We hope that you will agree that a good balance between an attractive design with dynamic and user-friendly content, has been found.

Copenhagen was the location for our DARIAH General Virtual Competency Centre meeting this year, hosted by our DARIAH colleagues in Denmark. Over 70 people from 14 different countries participating in the meeting, including colleagues from our network of affiliated projects such as CENDARI, EHRI, ARIADNE and DiXiT. As an infrastructure developed by researchers, for researchers, the showcase of some of Denmark's digital research activities provided a perfect backdrop for the event.

And last but not least, in December 2013, the first calls from the European Commission's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Horizon 2020 were launched. We can already see that the Research Infrastructures Work Programme will be of particular relevance for DARIAH, which, we are sure, is something we can look forward to reporting on next year.

Dr. Laurent Romary,
Director, DARIAH-EU

Dr. Tobias Blanke,
Director, DARIAH-EU

Dr. Conny Kristel
Director, DARIAH-EU

2. Key Objectives for 2013

In 2013 DARIAH has taken significant steps to **enable digital arts and humanities research** by **developing a sustainable infrastructure** by integrating existing resources, tools and services for the European arts and humanities research community and beyond. For 2013, our key objectives were:

1. **Take significant steps towards establishing the DARIAH ERIC**
2. **Increase visibility of DARIAH activities throughout Europe**
3. **Integrate and coordinate national DARIAH activities at the European level**
4. **Organise the scientific and technical integration of DARIAH activities**
5. **Implement interim governance structure for the DARIAH ERIC**
6. **Identify opportunities for DARIAH in Horizon 2020**

The following pages of this report highlight the key achievements that DARIAH has made against these objectives in 2013.

3. Key achievements in 2013

Here is an overview of the key achievements against our objectives in 2013:

3.1. Take significant steps towards establishing the DARIAH ERIC

2013 has been a significant year for putting the foundation stones in place for establishing DARIAH as a European legal entity, the DARIAH ERIC. The [European Research Infrastructure Consortium \(ERIC\) legal framework](#) is designed to facilitate the joint establishment and operation of European research infrastructures.

In January 2013, France received the formal feedback from the European Commission on the DARIAH-ERIC Step 1 application following the evaluation by the Independent Expert Group in December. DARIAH received a positive evaluation requiring some amendments to the draft DARIAH-ERIC Statutes and the Technical and Scientific Description.

The first quarter of the year was dedicated to revising the documents based on the recommendations following the Step 1 evaluation. The revised documents were reviewed by legal experts in France and the European Commission. Regarding the Statutes, the majority of the changes were minor and can be summarised as follows:

1. **EC template** - the statutes have been implemented in the new EC template
2. **Budgetary model** - the method for calculating the budgetary model has been simplified and transferred to an Annex
3. **Governance structure** - this better reflects the reality of DARIAH, ensuring efficient and effective decision-making and working relations

One of the most challenging tasks was transferring the DARIAH ERIC Statutes to a new template provided by the European Commission. However, this led to a simplified and easier to implement set of statutes. The more detailed information about the operation of the ERIC and the different policies that guide the implementation could be transferred to an Internal Rules of Procedure.

In September the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESR) circulated the template ‘Letter of Commitment’ to enable each of the future Founding Member countries to formally support France’s request to the European Commission to establish the DARIAH ERIC. By the end of 2013, Letters of Commitment from nine countries, Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, The Netherlands and Slovenia, had been received. Until the European Commission freezes the documents, approximately, there is still the opportunity for additional countries to join as Founding Members.

Just before the end of the year, in December 2013, the ERIC regulation was amended (cf. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/JOHtml.do?uri=OJ:L:2013:326:SOM:EN:HTML>). As a result, the DARIAH ERIC Statutes had to be updated to take these amendments into account.

3.2. Increase visibility of DARIAH activities throughout Europe

Launch of the new DARIAH-EU website

The DARIAH-EU website is the key focus for communications activities for the DARIAH community. Anyone participating in DARIAH or interested in DARIAH should be able to come to the DARIAH-EU website and find easily the information they are looking for.

A key goal for the new DARIAH-EU website was to make it a first entry point for DH scholars, researchers, DARIAH partner institutions and partner projects to get high-quality information about DH services from DARIAH partner institutions. It is also the intention to show DARIAH-EU as a living and well-used infrastructure.

Following a detailed conceptualisation, design and implementation process, the new DARIAH-EU website was launched at the DARIAH General Virtual Competency Centre (VCC) meeting in September 2013. The following paragraphs provide an overview of the different sections of the new website:

About: this section of the website focuses on DARIAH as a European organisation. Once established, this will become the official website of the DARIAH-ERIC. For example, the ‘Our Partners’ page visualises which countries are Members of DARIAH, with the possibility of finding more information, including the details of partner institutions that participating in a particular country. In addition, information about the DARIAH organisation, for example, pictures and contact details of the different people involved in the governance and coordination of DARIAH. There is also a section about ‘Joining DARIAH’ to help new countries, partner institutions or researchers, to get involved.

Contributions: this is the place where DARIAH partner institutions and affiliated projects can showcase their tools, services and expertise (e.g. CENDARI, DIGHUMLAB, EASY, ISIDORE, Open Edition and TextGrid). There is an attractive carousel, which dynamically displays each contributions’ logo, a short textual description as well as a link to specific page describing the contribution in detail. Anticipating the future, a powerful full-text search engine (based on Apache SOLR) has been implemented, to enable users of the website to search through the wide range of contributions. With 13 Member countries to date and each country with at least 2 or 3 partner institutions, and in some cases more than 20, it is important that a scalable way of presenting this information is provided.

Activities: provides information about the activities of each of DARIAH's Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs). A particularly important feature of this section is the opportunity to 'meet the VCC team'. For each VCC, a photograph of the key team members is provided, including their areas of expertise and activities within DARIAH. It is also possible to contact the VCC teams directly via the website. A key activity in the DARIAH calendar is the annual General VCC meeting. The activities section of the website is where details of the [DARIAH General VCC meetings](#) are published. It also functions as an archive of the past events.

Library: is the place where people can find DARIAH's key documents and resources. From the formal documentation, for example the DARIAH Scientific and Technical description or the DARIAH-ERIC Statutes, to researcher-orientated information such as the DARIAH-EU Leaflet or Information Brochure. Additionally, resources such as the DARIAH-EU logos are provided for download. The complete archive of the DARIAH-EU Transition Bulletin is available for download, as well as selected presentations and publications about DARIAH by colleagues from all over Europe.

News: This is the most dynamic part of the website, where regular news items events (e.g. conferences, workshops, symposia and summer schools), jobs, as well as fellowships and scholarships are announced. These news items are provided by DARIAH partner institutions, affiliated projects and by the wider DH community. In the articles section, more in-depth news items are published. The news section also includes dynamic updates, for example from the DARIAH-EU twitter feed.

DARIAH-EU website homepage

DARIAH-EU on Twitter

The [DARIAH-EU Twitter account](#) was launched in August 2012 and by December 2012, DARIAH-EU already had 154 followers. Twitter proved to be a very popular communication channel for the DARIAH community as by the end of 2013, this figure had increased by 565 to over 719 followers. With the launch of the new DARIAH-EU website, a

'Twitter update', has been implemented. This module allows the tweets from the DARIAH-EU twitter stream to be automatically published at various places on the DARIAH-EU website (e.g. homepage, news page etc.). Communicating via Twitter seems to be very popular with the DARIAH community. Other DARIAH Member countries (e.g. [DARIAH-DE](#)) have also created Twitter accounts. DARIAH-EU will continue its effort to use the twitter account as a key communications tool in 2014. Although other social media options are available, at this stage, Twitter seems to be the preferred social media channel for the DARIAH community.

Distributed Access to Partners' Contributions

For partner institutions increased visibility of their expertise, projects and services is an important benefit of participating in DARIAH. For the digital arts and humanities community, it is essential to know what DARIAH has to offer and also how they may contribute. In 2013, VCC3 Scholarly Content Management initiated a project to investigate how distributed access to partner contributions could be realised using linked data technologies. The initial results were [presented](#) at the DARIAH-EU General VCC meeting in Copenhagen in September 2013.

Calenda.org

The partnership with Calenda, Open Edition's online announcement service from DARIAH Partner Institution, Cléo (Centre for open electronic publishing). In December 2013, the DARIAH-EU Communications Officer, the Calenda team and the DARIAH-FR coordination team met in Paris to explore how to align the DARIAH / Calenda workflows and procedures. A Calenda Policy document has been created to provide a framework, as well as practical guidelines, for the DARIAH/Calenda collaboration. The goal is to publish announcements that have been entered into Calenda by DARIAH partners automatically on the DARIAH-EU website using the Calenda API.

3.3. Integrate and coordinate national DARIAH activities at the European level

National Coordinators Meeting: A first meeting of the future DARIAH National Coordinators took place on 8 July at the [Centre Marc Bloch](#) in Berlin. The aim of the meeting, which was attended by 21 people from 14 countries, was to brief the National Coordinators on the 'Step 2 application' and outline what is required from each of their countries.

Following a friendly welcome by the Centre's Director, [Patrice Veit](#), DARIAH Director Tobias Blanke took colleagues step-by-step through the DARIAH ERIC application process encouraging feedback and questions to ensure clear understanding of the process and supporting documentation. The National Coordinators then took the floor to present the DARIAH activities that are taking place in their country within the context of national priorities for digital arts and humanities.

Once established, a key task of the National Coordinator Committee will be to create an Annual Synthesis of the DARIAH National Roadmaps. As a first step towards this, the National Coordinators produced a document entitled ***Towards Founding Members of the DARIAH ERIC.***

Towards Founding Membership of the DARIAH ERIC

DARIAH-EU Coordination Office
September 2013

This document intends to introduce the future Founding Members of DARIAH by providing an overview per country of:

- the national priorities for digital arts and humanities
- national DARIAH activities including partner organisations and areas of expertise

A special highlight of the National Coordinators meeting was the presentations from ‘candidate countries’, Belgium, Lithuania and Switzerland. Building on the common themes drawn out of the presentations of national activities, the meeting ended with looking towards the future and developing a common vision for DARIAH, particularly in the context of the upcoming Horizon 2020 calls. Once DARIAH is established as a European organisation,

the National Coordinator Committee will be one of the key operational organs of the DARIAH ERIC with special responsibility for integrating and coordinating DARIAH activities at the National level.

3.4. Organise the scientific and technical integration of DARIAH activities

DARIAH General VCC Meeting in Copenhagen

Over 70 people from 14 countries attended the 3rd DARIAH General VCC meeting in Copenhagen on 5-6 September 2013. The General VCC meeting, the annual ‘technical’ meeting of DARIAH, is an opportunity for colleagues to meet each other face to face, this time, in the late summer sun of Copenhagen, Denmark. This General VCC meeting is the third of its kind, following Utrecht in April 2012 and Vienna in November 2012.

For researchers, by researchers

As Denmark were our hosts for the 2013 General VCC meeting, the Danish Digital Humanities lab (DIGHUMLAB) provided us with a showcase of the digital scholarly activities in Denmark. In his [presentation](#), Mads Rosendahl Thomsen, from the University of Aarhus, explored *what do literary scholars need from DH?* For him, a key questions when exploring the relationship between literature and digital humanities is whether digital methods offer support or are a main approach. Dr. Rosendahl Thomsen’s research includes a new Mellon-funded research grant to study the impact of French Literature in Scandinavia, using digital methods.

At the other end of the spectrum Mads Kähler Holst from the Moesgård Museum and University of Aarhus, [presented](#) how digital technologies have impacted on archaeological excavation. He showed the possibilities of visualising geo-referenced patterns of find distribution, linked with digital photographs and enriched with external data sources such

as sites and monument records. He emphasising the IT preconditions that are needed to enable archaeology to go digital.

Education and Training

In order to develop a research infrastructure that meets the needs of the research community we are trying to serve, it is therefore very important that we develop a research infrastructure based on the current research practices in digital arts and humanities. In the session on the [Scholarly Methods Ontology](#), Panos Constantopoulos (DARIAH-GR) and Matt Munson (DARIAH-DE) shared the current work that is being undertaken on understanding research practices. This work forms the basis for a taxonomy of digital humanities research activities.

Within a European context, the important of providing multilingual training materials and that 'DARIAH must be an infrastructure for all humanists, not just the digital ones' was emphasised by Toma Tasovac (DARIAH-RS). Other activities included a registry of 'DH Programmes' and an exploration of whether specific training (e.g. TEI) or more 'general humanist' training is needed.

Increasing visibility

As a distributed infrastructure, it is important that DARIAH is not fragmented. The aim of the 'experiment' to provide [Distributed access to partners' contributions](#) was to 'Improve research opportunities and outcomes through linking distributed digital source materials of many kinds'. For contributors, to increase the visibility of their contributions. For researchers, to give them the tools to help find relevant information for their research. Currently, the [Isidore](#) triplestore includes 15 contributions from 5 countries and two from DARIAH Affiliated projects. The next step is to encourage more DARIAH partners to participate as well as exploring how the contribution can be made available via the DARIAH-EU website.

Shared Technology Platform

A shared technology platform is an important part of the DARIAH Infrastructure. In the [preservation](#) sessions, presentations from Germany, Austria, Ireland and France explored the different technologies needed for preservation of research data and for data curation. During the [Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure \(AAI\) session](#), the work underway to assess the potential of collaborating with [EduGain](#) was explored.

The [controlled vocabularies](#) session, built on the activities of the working group that had been established during the General VCC meeting in Vienna. A main goal of the group is to build a comprehensive infrastructure for harmonised provision and collaborative maintenance of controlled vocabularies and reference data for the DARIAH (and Digital Humanities) community.

Opportunities in the changing publications landscape

The changing publications landscape in the arts and humanities was a hot topic during the meeting. With traditional scholarly publishing no longer meeting the needs of today's humanities researchers, alternative publication platforms are needed. In the [Publications and Open Access](#) session, led by Marin Dacos (DARIAH-FR) and Christof Schöch (DARIAH-DE), various publications platforms, which help humanities researchers achieve recognition and visibility for their work, were explored.

Working with research communities

In the penultimate session of the meeting, there was an opportunity to hear from some of the research communities that DARIAH is actively working with. Along with EHRI and CENDARI, we heard the latest news from the newer players in the game, ARIADNE (Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Data Networking in Europe) and DiXiT (Digital Scholarly Editions Initial Training Network). Looking towards the future and the next round of research funding under the European Commission's Horizon 2020 funding we heard from Netlab, who are the coordinators of RESAW, the future Research Infrastructure for the Study of Archived Web materials.

Key recommendations for an action plan included:

- DARIAH to explore the use of the Open Edition scholarly publishing platforms, e.g. scholarly blogging platform ([Hypotheses.org](#)) and scholarly event platform ([Calenda.org](#)).
- DARIAH to use the [HAL Open Access Archive](#) as an open archive for DARIAH.
- DARIAH to continue to increase the visibility of partner contributions using Linked Open Data technologies such as those used in [Isidore](#).

3.5. Implement an interim governance structure for the DARIAH ERIC

Establish an interim Senior Management Team for DARIAH

With the final stages of establishing the DARIAH ERIC in sight, the Board of Directors felt that it was important to put an interim Senior Management Team (SMT) in place. To ensure that DARIAH is able to operate as a European organisation once the legal entity is in place there is much preparatory work to be done. The SMT will consist of the Chair and Vice-Chair of the National Coordinator Committee (NCC) and the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the Joint Research Committee (JRC). In addition, the Chair of the Scientific Board and the relevant officers of the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office (DCO) will be invited to SMT meetings.

The interim Senior Management Team is:

NCC Chair: Charly Mörth (DARIAH-AT)

NCC Vice-Chair: Luca Pezzati (DARIAH-IT)

JRC Chair: Henk Harmsen (Chief Organisation Officer)

JRC Vice-Chair: Sophie David (DARIAH-FR)

3.6. Identify opportunities for DARIAH in Horizon 2020

In 2012, the European Commission conducted a [consultation](#) on possible topics for future activities for integrating and opening national research infrastructures. DARIAH-EU took an active role in raising awareness of the consultation within the European arts and humanities community and to encourage particular communities to respond to the consultation. The [consultation assessment report](#) was published in March 2013, identified 14 topics of high potential within social sciences and humanities, many of which had been instigated by DARIAH partner institutions.

In December 2013, the European Commission published the [Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2014-2015 for Research Infrastructures](#). This is one of the key Work Programmes that could be directly relevant for DARIAH. At least three calls that could be directly relevant for DARIAH have already been identified:

- **INFRADEV-3-2015:** Individual implementation and operation of ESFRI projects; deadline January 2015; up to 15 million euro
- **INFRADEV-4-2014/2015:** Implementation and operation of cross-cutting services and solutions for clusters of ESFRI and other relevant research infrastructure initiatives; deadline 2 September 2014; 6 – 15 million euro.
- **INFRAIA-1-2014/2015:** Integrating and opening existing national and regional research infrastructures of European interest; deadline 2 September 2014; 10 million euro; indicative budget call: 140 million euro

For **INFRAIA-1-2014/2015**, the two advanced communities in the Social Sciences and Humanities that were identified were:

- Contemporary European history: European Holocaust research infrastructure
- European research infrastructures for restoration & conservation of cultural heritage

Both of these communities are closely connected with DARIAH. The development of Horizon 2020 proposals will be a key activity for the DARIAH Senior Management Team in 2014.

4. DARIAH activities 2013: a visual journey

The following pages take you on a visual journey through 2013 for DARIAH. On a month-by-month basis, the highlights from DARIAH national activities, affiliated projects such as ARIADNE, CENDARI and EHRI as well as the European-level activities organised by DARIAH-EU are showcased.

30 January | Paris, France
Journée d'information DARIAH

07 February | Rome, Italy
Launch of ARIADNE

February
Italy signs Memorandum
of Understanding

4/5 April | Vilnius, Lithuania
Hack4LT – Cultural Heritage and
Digital Humanities hackathon

27 April | Toronto Canada
DARIAH @ HASTAC 2013: “Understanding and
Building a Community: DARIAH-EU’s Virtual
Competency Centre for Research and Education”

17 June | Dublin, Ireland
Irish EU Presidency event

17 June | Ljubljana, Slovenia
DARIAH-SI (SIDIH) workshop
on “Copyright in digital age”

19 June | Dublin, Ireland
Meeting of the joint DARIAH/NeDiMah
ICT Methods Taxonomy Working Group

26/27 June | Aarhus, Denmark
Cultural Heritage Creative Tools And Archives Workshop

08 July | Berlin, Germany
DARIAH-EU National
Coordinator's meeting

Luca Pezzati,
Laurent Romary
and Tobias Blanke

9 July | Berlin, Germany
Joint DARIAH/EHRI Conference: Public
History of the Holocaust, Historical
Research in the digital age

Conny Kristel

15 July – 09 August | Paris and Munich
EHRI Summer Schools in Holocaust Studies

16–19 July | Nebraska, U.S.
Digital Humanities 2013 “The DARIAH Approach to
Interdisciplinary Interoperability”, “DARIAH-EU's Virtual
Competency Center for Teaching and Research”

22-26 July | Florence, Italy
CENDARI Summer School 2013

19 – 23 August | Göttingen, Germany
DARIAH-DE International DH Summer School
“A one-week crash course in using the
scripting language Python”

5/6 September | Copenhagen, Denmark
3rd DARIAH-EU General VCC meeting

09 September
Launch of the new DARIAH-EU website

5. DARIAH team 2013

DARIAH-EU Board of Directors (BoD)

Laurent Romary
Director

Tobias Blanke
Director

Conny Kristel
Director

DARIAH-EU Interim Senior Management Team (SMT)

Karlheinz Mörth
National Coordinator
Committee Chair

Luca Pezzati
National Coordinator
Committee Vice-Chair

Henk Harmsen
Joint Research Committee
Chair

Sophie David
Joint Research Committee
Vice-Chair

DARIAH-EU Coordination Office

Sally Chambers
Secretary General

Gabriele Kraft
Communications
Officer

Kristine Voigt
Technical Support Officer